

Performance of AI Oriented Contrastive Learning vs Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in Quality Assessment of Zinc Coating Steel Coils

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Abstract—Zinc-coated steel coil quality inspection is critical within the automotive and construction industries, where coating defect affects durability and safety. This study compares Contrastive Learning with Convolutional Neural Networks for the identification of defects in 4,482 coil profiles against zinc thickness measurements. CNNs, including normalization and pooling layers, delivered high accuracy (F1-score: 0.93 test, 0.75 gold-standard), and contrastive learning, utilizing Siamese networks, demonstrated less but improvable performance (F1-score: 0.61 raw, 0.66 preprocessed). CNNs perform well when there is abundant labeled data, while contrastive learning improves feature representation with scarce supervision. The results indicate the potential of AI for real-time quality control and the importance of data preprocessing to maximize model performance.

Zinc Coating, Industrial Inspection, Quality Control, Contrastive Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Zinc-coated steel coils play a pivotal role in multiple industries, such as automotive, construction, and appliance manufacturing by providing superior corrosion resistance and overall durability [1], [2].

Galvanized steel coils are manufactured by applying a protective zinc coating to steel, significantly enhancing their corrosion resistance and extending their service life [3]. As shown in Figure 1, the hot-dip galvanizing process involves immersing steel in a bath of molten zinc. This method, in particular, offers numerous advantages, including outstanding durability, exceptional strength, and superior weather resistance [4]. These attributes make galvanized steel coils a preferred material across various industries, underscoring the critical importance of quality control.

Fig. 1. Hot-Dip-Galvanizing-Line [5]

In the automotive sector, for instance, galvanized steel is critical for ensuring vehicle safety and durability, making rigorous quality control processes essential. Traditionally, as shown in Figure 2, these processes rely on visual inspections by human operators or rule-based systems, supplemented by technologies like X-ray gauges and high-definition cameras that use measurements such as thickness gauges [6]. However, such methods are labor-intensive, prone to human error, and often struggle to handle the high variability and volume of modern production lines.

Fig. 2. Inspection System [5]

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) solutions have gained traction as an effective means to automate and enhance the accuracy of quality inspection [7]. Among various AI approaches, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have become a cornerstone of image-based classification and defect detection tasks because of their ability to learn hierarchical feature representations from large datasets [7]. Despite their success, CNNs typically demand extensive labeled data—a resource that is both expensive and time consuming to obtain in industrial contexts. To address the challenges associated with limited labeled data, contrastive learning (CL) has emerged as a self-supervised learning technique capable of leveraging unlabeled samples [8]. By comparing pairs of “similar” (positive) and “dissimilar” (negative) examples, contrastive learning discovers meaningful feature embeddings without relying solely on large amounts of annotated data [9]. This characteristic makes CL an attractive alternative in industrial settings, where annotation costs can be prohibitive and defect classes are highly imbalanced [10]. Against this backdrop, this paper systematically compares CNN-based and contrastive learning approaches for quality assessment of zinc-coated steel coils. We examine performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, and also evaluate the robustness of each model to noise and data variability. Beyond the technical evaluation, we discuss the practical implications of deploying these methods in real-world manufacturing lines, aligning our findings with the emergent trends of Industry 4.0 and Industry 5.0, where intelligent automation is paramount.

II. STATE OF ART

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have revolutionized the field of computer vision and have found extensive applications in industrial inspection [7]. Their ability to automatically extract hierarchical features from images by applying various layers (Figure 3) makes them particularly suited for tasks such as defect detection and classification [11].

In the context of manufacturing quality control, CNNs have been employed to identify surface defects, measure coating thickness, and categorize different types of imperfections [12]. Recent advancements have focused on optimizing CNN architectures for real-time processing on embedded hardware, enhancing their applicability in industrial settings [11].

Fig. 3. CNN Layers

Contrastive learning, a self-supervised learning paradigm, has emerged as a powerful technique for learning representations from data without the need for extensive labeled datasets [8]. This approach involves training models to distinguish between similar and dissimilar data pairs, thereby learning invariant and discriminative features [10].

Contrastive learning has been successfully applied in various domains, including natural image classification, medical imaging, and industrial inspection [13]. In industrial settings where labeled data is often difficult to get, contrastive learning offers a promising solution by leveraging both labeled and unlabeled data to train robust models [14]. In the specific domain of zinc coating steel quality assessment, traditional methods rely on image processing techniques and conventional machine learning algorithms to detect defects such as micro-cracks and uneven coating [12]. However, these methods often struggle with the variability in image conditions and the complexity of defect patterns, leading to suboptimal performance [15].

The integration of deep learning techniques, including CNNs and contrastive learning, represents a significant advancement in handling this variability while maintaining high accuracy [16]. Additionally, contrastive learning frameworks, such as Siamese net-

works, have shown promise in one-shot learning for defect classification [17].

Despite these advances, the application of contrastive learning in industrial inspection is still nascent and faces challenges related to data scarcity and computational demands [18]. This study aims to contribute to this evolving field by providing a comprehensive comparison of CNNs and contrastive learning approaches for quality assessment of zinc coating steel coils. By evaluating their performance under varying conditions and data availability, this research seeks to offer insights into the most effective strategies for implementing AI-driven quality control in manufacturing processes.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Design Science Research (DSR) Approach

This research adheres to the principles of Design Science Research (DSR), drawing on structured methodologies highlighted by [19], [20]. By following DSR, the study pursues a systematic cycle of problem identification, artifact creation, evaluation, and result dissemination within the specific context of zinc coating quality assessment.

First, we clearly identified a persistent problem in industrial manufacturing, which is the difficulty of achieving accurate and efficient detection of defects in zinc-coated steel coils, especially when labeled data are limited. Next, we defined our research objectives, focusing on developing machine learning models—both Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Contrastive Learning (CL) frameworks—to enhance feature extraction and classification robustness.

Under the design and development phase, we formulated a dual-strategy approach, which includes a CNN that relies on extensive labeled data, and a CL method capable of leveraging unlabeled data through self-supervised or semi-supervised learning. In order to demonstrate and evaluate these artifacts, we tested both models on a dataset of zinc coating images, comparing metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. We also assessed each model's practical feasibility by examining

computational overhead and sensitivity to data transformations.

Finally, as per DSR guidelines, we communicate our outcomes in both academic and industrial forums, discussing model performance, limitations, and possible avenues for integration into existing manufacturing processes. This iterative DSR cycle ensures that our solutions align with real-world requirements, thus bridging the gap between theoretical development and applied engineering practice.

B. CRISP-DM Framework

In parallel with DSR, we employed the Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) [21] to structure our data-centric tasks and maintain rigor in model development and evaluation. As can be seen

Fig. 4. Methodology CRISP-DM

in Figure 4, this methodology includes several steps as follows:

- **Business Understanding:** We aligned the research with the operational needs of zinc coating inspection, recognizing that reduced downtime and improved defect detection accuracy translate into substantial cost savings and enhanced product quality.
- **Data Understanding:** Initial assessments of the zinc coating image dataset revealed various defect types, those ranging from cracks to inconsistent thickness, and underscored the importance of handling class imbalance.

- **Data Preparation:** We implemented normalization, augmentation such as rotations, flips, scaling, and row/column permutations, and optional segmentation masks for defective samples. These steps aimed to minimize the effects of lighting and positional variance while also addressing class imbalance.
- **Modeling:** We then developed CNN and CL models, conducting grid searches to tune hyperparameters such as learning rate and batch size. Model depth ranged from three to ten convolutional layers, and the placement of pooling, normalization, and dense layers was systematically varied to identify optimal designs.
- **Evaluation** Performance was measured through cross-validation and a final assessment on a gold standard set of images. Metrics such as F1-score, precision, recall, and ROC/AUC were used to capture both classification accuracy and model robustness.
- **Deployment:** Although the focus of this study is empirical evaluation, the eventual aim is to integrate the best-performing solution into an industrial inspection pipeline, emphasizing scalability and ease of maintenance.

IV. PROPOSED SOLUTION

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

The data utilized in this study was provided by an industrial partner, who shared a pre-collected, processed, and manually labeled set of coil measurements. Each coil was assessed based on zinc coating thickness, categorized either as acceptable (OK) or non-acceptable (NOK) by experienced operators (Figure 5). Nine sensors on each side of the coil captured these thickness measurements, resulting in 264 readings per sensor, which we established as a fixed parameter to enable efficient tensor operations.

To achieve this uniform dimension, each coil’s length was segmented into 264 parts; coils that were shorter thus yielded a higher sampling density. Consequently, each coil produced a matrix of size 264×18 (nine sensors on each side), and combining multiple

Fig. 5. Zinc Measures

coils led to a dataset shaped as $(N, 264, 18)$, where N is the total number of coils .

An inherent challenge in this dataset was class imbalance, as the manufacturing process typically yields a higher proportion of OK coils. To address this, we applied data augmentation techniques [22], including random row and column permutations, among other transformations. This step was crucial for increasing the number of NOK samples and helping the models generalize more effectively to unseen cases [23].

After augmentation, the main dataset comprised 4,482 images, which were partitioned into training, validation, and test subsets for model development and hyperparameter tuning. In addition to these subsets, a curated “gold standard” set of 60 images (30 OK and 30 NOK) was set aside, following the methodology suggested in [24]. This gold standard subset allows different models to be compared on an identical, unbiased reference, thereby offering a more definitive assessment of their predictive performance.

B. CNN Implementation

For the CNN-based solution, we designed an adaptable framework capable of generating different network configurations from a YAML specification file. Each configuration defines key parameters such as the number of convolutional layers (ranging from 3 to 10), the placement of pooling and normalization layers, dropout probabilities, and the depth of fully connected layers. Convolutional layers typically use ReLU activations, with kernel

sizes and numbers of filters adjusted to capture both coarse and fine-grained features of the zinc coating.

Once a configuration is parsed, a CNN model is constructed using the TensorFlow deep learning library. During training, we employ a categorical cross-entropy loss and an optimizer, refining hyperparameters through grid search or validation feedback. To ensure statistical robustness, each configuration undergoes 5-fold cross-validation, repeated up to 10 times, thus generating multiple performance measures, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC/AUC. We further validate top performing models on a dedicated “gold-standard” set of 60 images, providing an additional checkpoint for borderline defect cases. This systematic approach to CNN architecture design and evaluation establishes a reliable baseline for automated zinc-coated coil classification.

C. Contrastive Learning Implementation

To overcome the limitations of limited labeled data and to exploit unlabeled samples, we integrated contrastive learning into our proposed solution in two principal ways. The first approach was SimCLR-inspired, where each image was augmented twice to form a positive pair, and images drawn from different samples served as negatives. A CNN backbone extracted features, which were then projected into a latent space via a small MLP head. Training relied on the NT-Xent loss, pushing positive pairs closer in the embedding space while separating negative pairs.

The second approach employed a Siamese network, in which two identical CNN encoders processed image pairs to produce embeddings. Positive pairs included two images from the same class (“OK” or “NOK”), while negative pairs mixed classes. To facilitate classification, reference images for each class were identified using clustering algorithms such as DBSCAN or KMeans, enabling new samples to be classified based on similarity metrics.

Once each cluster was formed, representative images that best characterized the center

Fig. 6. Example of how embeddings from the same class form a single cluster

of these clusters were chosen to serve as references for class assignment.

Fig. 7. Visualization of multiple clusters for OK and NOK classes using DBSCAN

After either type of contrastive pretraining which are SimCLR or Siamese, the encoder underwent a fine tuning phase with cross-entropy loss on the labeled dataset to finalize class predictions. This two stage process allowed us to leverage both labeled and unlabeled data more effectively, particularly in situations where annotated samples were limited.

D. Training and Evaluation

The implementation used TensorFlow and keras Python-based deep learning libraries and took advantage of multi-GPU training

for efficient experimentation. We systematically measured accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, ROC/AUC, and inference time on both the test set and a highly curated gold standard subset of 60 images. The CNN models generally exhibited strong baseline performance with abundant labeled data, while the contrastive learning methods showed enhanced robustness, especially in identifying subtle defects and handling data scarcity.

V. RESULT

A. CNN Model Performance

The study began by testing a wide array of CNN configurations which initially several thousand, to explore the effects of varying convolutional layers (3 to 10), dense layers (3 to 11), and hyperparameters such as kernel sizes and dropout rates. Although deeper networks often performed better, most architectures still attained high accuracy and F1-scores, indicating that CNNs are well-suited to discerning acceptable (OK) from non-acceptable (NOK) coils. For instance, Figure 8 illustrates how adding more convolutional layers tends to improve classification, particularly when detecting borderline defects.

Fig. 8. Architecture Comparison

Despite these improvements, hyperparameter changes like adjusting kernel sizes or increasing dropout, generally yielded only minor differences, a conclusion supported by Shapiro–Wilk and t-tests statistical tests. In other words, CNNs of moderate to high depth could achieve similarly robust results, suggesting that overall design simplicity may be more important than fine-grained hyperparameter tweaks. The top architectures attained

F1-scores above 0.90 on the main test set, yet on the smaller “gold standard” set of 60 curated images, their performance saw a modest dip, dropping to around 0.75–0.80. This gap underscores the difficulty of capturing subtle edge cases. As shown in Figure 9, confusion matrices confirm that most errors arise from classifying marginal NOK samples as OK (or vice versa), highlighting the nuanced nature of real-world zinc-coating defects. Overall, the CNN approach delivers strong, consistent results and provides a solid foundation for automated quality assessment in steel-coil manufacturing processes.

Fig. 9. DL Mean Confusion Matrix Test Set

B. Contrastive. Learning Model Performance

In contrast to the CNN approach, Contrastive Learning (CL) was explored through two main frameworks: a Siamese network and a SimCLR-inspired model. A total of 24 architectures were tested, each varying in convolutional layers (3 to 10), dropout rates, and pooling/normalization strategies. Although several configurations reached F1-scores above 0.60 on the main test set, many struggled to maintain consistency on the smaller gold standard of 60 images, occasionally overclassifying most coils into a single category (often NOK). This discrepancy exposed a key fragility: while certain setups excelled on the broader data, they did not necessarily translate their gains to more challenging borderline cases.

Deeper encoders generally extracted richer features, particularly from the original 264×18 matrices, yet simpler models (3 convolutional

layers) performed competitively when images were resized to 264×264. Normalization and pooling (whether partial or full) proved beneficial in stabilizing the learned embeddings, although Figure 10 and Figure 11 demonstrate that omitting these strategies usually led to noticeable performance drops. Dropout produced mixed outcomes: some architectures tolerated a 0.3–0.5 dropout well, while others showed better discrimination without it. Ultimately, the best CL models still lagged slightly behind the top CNN configurations when tested on the gold standard set, suggesting that further tuning through tailored augmentations or more robust embeddings could help bridge the gap.

Fig. 10. CL Pooling Type

Fig. 11. CL Normalization Type

C. Comparative Analysis of CNN and Contrastive Learning

In evaluating zinc coating quality, CNNs consistently emerged as the stronger baseline. On the main test set, the best CNN achieved an F1-score between 0.89 and 0.93, with accuracy around 92–93%. Notably, its precision ranged from 90% to 94%, indicating a relatively low rate of false positives,

while recall hovered between 88% and 92%. Inference times generally remained near 45 ms per image, which is suitable for near real-time inspection in industrial settings. However, performance did drop on the gold standard of 60 curated images, with F1-scores settling around 0.70–0.75. The primary cause of these misclassifications seemed to be the model’s difficulty in distinguishing borderline defect cases, where slight deviations in zinc thickness could appear superficially similar to acceptable samples.

By contrast, Contrastive Learning (CL) methods—encompassing both Siamese networks and SimCLR-inspired frameworks demonstrated varying degrees of success. Some deeper architectures achieved test-set F1-scores exceeding 0.60 (and occasionally nearer to 0.66 when using 264×264 images), but a few runs overfit by classifying most samples as non-acceptable (NOK), thus inflating recall at the expense of precision. On the gold standard set, the stronger CL models posted F1-scores around 0.61–0.66, which fell short of the top CNN’s performance. CL’s main advantage lies in its ability to exploit unlabeled data by learning robust feature embeddings, but it proved sensitive to hyperparameters, such as dropout and normalization. Models that omitted pooling or normalization entirely tended to degrade more severely, underscoring the importance of architecture tuning.

Comparing their robustness to subtle defects illustrates a key distinction: while CNNs tended to balance precision and recall across most configurations, CL models sometimes excelled on one metric (often recall) by overclassifying coils into the NOK category. This imbalance suggests that while CL can capture complex visual patterns, particularly in data limited scenarios, it may be more susceptible to large errors if improperly calibrated. Furthermore, on borderline samples that required especially fine discrimination, CNNs generally maintained better F1-scores.

Thus, if abundant labeled data is available and real time performance is paramount, CNNs provide a more consistently accurate solution. However, when labeling resources

are limited, CL approaches potentially offer a way to leverage unlabeled examples for enhanced feature learning, albeit with a higher risk of unstable classification unless carefully tuned and augmented. Future research that integrates CL pretraining with CNN fine tuning alongside more sophisticated data augmentation, may help unify these strengths and address the challenges each method faces on subtle, borderline defects.

VI. DISCUSSION

The experimental outcomes underscore the potential of advanced deep learning methodologies for automated zinc coating quality assessment. Specifically, the CNN-based approach demonstrated a strong capacity to handle large, well-annotated datasets, delivering high accuracy, precision, and recall on the primary test set. Its hierarchical feature extraction effectively isolated most defects, suggesting that, with sufficient labeled data, a well-designed CNN can robustly distinguish acceptable (OK) from non acceptable (NOK) steel coils. However, its performance drop on the gold standard subset of borderline samples indicates a lingering sensitivity to subtle thickness variations, suggesting that purely supervised methods may need additional fine-tuning or domain-specific data augmentation.

In contrast, Contrastive Learning (CL) showed promise in leveraging unlabeled data and learning richer, self-supervised embeddings. This characteristic is particularly attractive in industrial scenarios where labeling costs are high or defect types are highly imbalanced. Nevertheless, the study revealed that CL solutions can suffer from unstable classification, sometimes overemphasizing a single class to boost recall at the expense of precision. Additionally, CL's performance consistently lagged behind CNNs when exposed to the gold standard images, highlighting challenges in capturing borderline defects without extensive hyperparameter tuning or domain-tailored transformations.

Despite these distinctions, the overarching results indicate complementary strengths in both approaches. CNNs shine in well structured tasks backed by significant labeling

efforts, while CL approaches facilitate robust representation learning in data limited environments. A particularly interesting avenue for future research may be to combine these paradigms. For instance, contrastive pretraining could create strong initial embeddings that a CNN fine-tunes on labeled data, potentially balancing the label efficiency of CL with the established supervised prowess of CNNs.

From a practical perspective, industrial stakeholders should carefully consider data availability, labeling resources, and the complexity of real-world defects when choosing an approach. CNNs offer consistent and often superior performance where ample labeled data can be secured, while CL excels in self-supervised feature extraction, albeit with a risk of instability if class distributions or defect variability deviate from training assumptions. In high throughput manufacturing contexts, inference speed becomes a deciding factor: our results confirm that CNNs can achieve near real-time performance (45 ms per image), though CL methods can be optimized with lighter encoders or more efficient augmentations.

Lastly, these findings align with broader Industry 5.0 goals, in which human expertise partners with automated intelligence to refine quality control processes. By positioning deep learning models as a tool rather than a replacement, human operators can focus on nuanced, high risk decisions, while the AI handles bulk classification. Integrating either approach into an agile, CRISP-DM informed workflow further allows iterative improvements as new defect classes arise or operating conditions shift.

Overall, this study underscores the value of advanced AI-driven inspection while illuminating key trade-offs between CNN based and contrastive learning based strategies. Going forward, more sophisticated data augmentation pipelines, hybrid model architectures, and real world pilot deployments will help clarify which combination of methods best addresses the persistent challenge of accurate, efficient zinc coating inspection.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper has examined two major AI methodologies those are Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Contrastive Learning (CL), for automated quality assessment of zinc-coated steel coils. Our findings show that CNNs consistently achieve high performance when robust, labeled datasets are available, combining strong accuracy, precision, and recall with manageable inference times that suit real-time industrial inspection. However, like many fully supervised methods, CNNs faced challenges in classifying subtle or borderline defects within a smaller “gold standard” dataset, indicating that additional data augmentation or more refined network designs may be needed to handle ambiguous defect profiles.

By contrast, Contrastive Learning demonstrated a capacity to extract meaningful embeddings from limited or unlabeled data, an important advantage in scenarios where labeling every coil is impractical or expensive. Nevertheless, some CL models exhibited instability when tested on edge case samples, reflecting the heightened sensitivity of their performance to architectural tuning, data preprocessing, and balanced class distributions.

Overall, both approaches underscore the potential of AI driven quality inspection in accelerating and improving the detection of zinc coating defects. The choice between CNNs and CL ultimately depends on operational constraints including labeling resources, production timelines, and the severity of borderline defects. Future investigations may focus on hybrid solutions that combine contrastive pretraining with supervised fine tuning, aiming to unify the label efficiency of CL with the mature performance characteristics of CNNs. Ultimately, continuous integration of these approaches into real world manufacturing environments, supported by iterative refinements, can contribute significantly to the evolving landscape of Industry 5.0 quality control.

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- All authors contributed to the study conception and design.

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